

A Real-Time Sybil Attack Detection for Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETS) Using Spatio-Temporal Learning and XGBoost

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Abstract—Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs) are a cornerstone of intelligent transportation systems (ITS), enabling decentralized vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication. However, their dynamic topology and infrastructure less design make VANETs vulnerable to serious security threats. One major threat is the Sybil attack, where a single malicious node creates multiple fake identities to manipulate network behavior and compromise safety critical services. This paper presents a scalable, learning-based Sybil detection framework that models VANETs as time-evolving graphs. Vehicles are characterized using spatio-temporal features derived from beacon messages, including displacement, speed variation, directional change, beacon frequency, trust score, and behavioral similarity score. To enhance detection accuracy, a lightweight similarity-based clustering mechanism is introduced to capture identity correlations without assuming prior knowledge of malicious nodes. An XGBoost classifier is used to learn decision boundaries from a labeled dataset constructed via OMNeT++ simulations. The model achieves over 96% accuracy with less than 4% false positive rate across various traffic densities, demonstrating robust generalization.

Index Terms—Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs), Sybil Attack Detection, Spatio-Temporal Learning, XGBoost

I. INTRODUCTION

Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs), are a big step forward in smart transportation systems. They're basically a special type of mobile network made to let cars talk to each other

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Vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and also to things like traffic lights or road signs Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) [1]. These decentralized, infrastructure-independent networks enable real-time data exchange among highly mobile nodes (i.e., vehicles), thereby supporting important applications such as collision avoidance, cooperative driving, traffic flow optimization, and emergency message dissemination. VANETs are known for their fast-changing network structure, the need for low delay in communication, and the fact that vehicles move at high speeds. They use wireless technologies like IEEE 802.11p, Dedicated Short-Range Communications (DSRC), and the newer Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) to make this communication possible. However, these very features introduce complex challenges related to routing stability, scalability, security, and Quality of Service (QoS) assurance [2].

Sybil attacks are a serious security problem in decentralized networks like VANETs. In this attack, one malicious vehicle pretends to be many different fake vehicles, trying to mess with how the network works and disrupt communication between real vehicles. An attacker can fake multiple vehicles to take too much control over how data is shared, how routes are picked, and how trust systems work. This can lead to problems like traffic being sent the wrong way, network slowdowns, or even parts of the system going down [3]. In VANET environments, this attack undermines the integrity of location-based services and cooperative safety applications by injecting false data or fabricating the presence of non-existent vehicles [4].

The proposed method presents a dynamic, learning-based framework for Sybil attack detection in VANETs by modeling the network as a time-evolving graph $G(t) = (V(t), E(t))$, where each node $v_i \in V(t)$ broadcasts beacon messages with

temporal attributes such as location, speed, and direction [5]. Sybil attackers are modeled as entities generating multiple falsified identities with correlated mobility patterns, and a labeled dataset is constructed using simulated ground truth via manual injection, attack scripts, and observer nodes. Feature vectors $\mathbf{x}^{(i)}$ are extracted from spatio-temporal variations, including displacement ΔLoc , speed fluctuation $\Delta Speed$, directional change ΔDir , beacon frequency f_{beacon} , and similarity-based clustering scores $SimScore$. To address class imbalance, Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) is applied for resampling. The detection task is formulated as a binary classification problem using the XGBoost algorithm [6], trained with regularized gradient boosting. The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- We propose a real-time Sybil detection framework for VANETs using spatio-temporal features extracted from beacon messages.
- We introduce a similarity-based clustering method that detects coordinated Sybil behavior without requiring global network knowledge.
- We achieve high detection accuracy, low false positive rates, and real-time performance validated through OMNeT++ simulations.

II. RELATED WORK

Rashid et al. [7] propose an adaptive real-time malicious-node detection framework for VANETs that couples a distributed multi-layer classifier with Apache Spark-based execution and evaluates multiple Machine Learning (ML) models—Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosted Trees (GBT), and Multilayer Perceptron Classifier (MLPC)—on OMNeT++/SUMO traffic simulations. Their system targets Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) behavior by streaming features from Roadside Units (RSUs) and achieves up to 99% accuracy while maintaining elastic throughput using Amazon Web Services (AWS). The architecture emphasizes cluster formation, RSU monitoring, and limited-memory BFGS (L-BFGS) optimization to sustain real-time detection under growing network size. The method offers real-time operation, high accuracy, scalability through distributed or cloud processing, and realistic simulation with standard co-simulators (SIM). However, it lacks real-world validation, provides limited attack coverage (mainly DDoS), faces dataset generalizability issues, and has unquantified resource overheads.

Ajin et al. [8] propose an Adaptive Bald Eagle Search Optimization (ABESO)-based Multi-Agent Deep Q Network (MA-DQN) model for Sybil attack detection in VANETs. The method uses Balanced Iterative Reducing and Clustering using Hierarchies (BIRCH) for robust clustering, Taylor-based Waterwheel Plant (TWP) for cluster head (CH) selection, and blockchain for secure communication. ABESO optimizes the MA-DQN to enhance detection accuracy and reduce false alarms. The advantage of this approach is its high detection performance, scalability, and secure data transmission, while

the disadvantage lies in its computational overhead, complex parameter tuning, and potential latency during real-time VANET operations.

Salam Hamdan et al. [9] proposed a hybrid algorithm for detecting Sybil attacks in VANETS by combining the footprint and privacy-preserving detection of abuses of pseudonyms (P2DAP) methods. The hybrid scheme uses encryption, authentication, and vehicle trajectory information, dynamically switching between the two methods based on vehicle speed to improve detection performance. The algorithm was implemented and tested using the Network Simulator 2 (NS2), with scenarios generated through Simulation of Urban MObility (SUMO) and Mobility model generator for Vehicular networks (MOVE) tools. The main advantage of this method is its high detection accuracy and adaptability to varying vehicle speeds and densities, effectively reducing false alarms and improving robustness against identity-based attacks. However, its disadvantages include the reliance on a fixed speed threshold for algorithm switching and the implementation complexity due to the use of Tool Command Language (TCL) scripting, which limits scalability and maintainability compared to structured programming languages such as C++ or Java.

Zhang et al. [10] proposed a Sybil detection and traceability method for vehicular ad hoc networks that uses basic safety message (BSM) packets to infer the true sender by comparing a spatiotemporal transmission-distance model with time-synchronized neighbor distances. A weighted integration strategy aggregates per-packet source predictions over short windows to stabilize decisions and use the uniqueness of the BSM sender. Simulations report real-time Sybil detection and attacker identification with precision above ninety-six percent and ninety-four percent, respectively. Advantages include no additional hardware, independence from attack and traffic density, and explicit traceability; disadvantages include sensitivity to errors in the spatiotemporal model, dependence on accurate time synchronization and positioning, and the need to tune thresholds in the integration strategy.

Sefati and Tabrizi et al. [11] propose a Sybil-attack detection method for VANETs that first flags inconsistent identities via neighbor checks, then has the RSU compute a fitness function over Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), End-to-End Delay (E2ED), energy, and packet loss, and finally validates suspects using Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) and throughput. Implemented in Network Simulator 3 (NS3) with Ad hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV) routing and User Datagram Protocol (UDP) traffic, the approach outperforms Probability Density Function (PDF)-based detection, Fuzzy-based Collaborative Verification System (FCVS), and a Heartbeat scheme in delay, detection accuracy, and dropped packets. The advantage is timely detection using readily available metrics (Received Signal Strength Indicator and throughput) without extra hardware. The disadvantage is sensitivity to channel variability and parameter tuning (weights/thresholds) and dependence on centralized RSU computation, with validation limited to NS3.

Fig. 1. A Sybil attack scenario in VANET

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

VANETs use real-time, decentralized communication between vehicles to help prevent accidents, ease traffic congestion, and support cooperative driving. These features are essential for creating safer and more efficient road systems [12]. But because these networks are open and don't rely on fixed infrastructure, they're especially vulnerable to Sybil attacks. In these cases, a malicious vehicle creates a bunch of fake identities to mess with routing decisions, flood the network, or spread false information [13]. Checking identity in VANETs is tough because there's no stable infrastructure and protecting privacy is a must. Many detection methods also fall short since they assume things like complete knowledge of every user or that vehicles follow predictable paths, which isn't how things work in reality. Figure 1 illustrates a Sybil attack scenario in a VANET environment, where a single attacker vehicle generates multiple fake identities (Sybil nodes) to create a false illusion of road congestion.

A. Metrics

To evaluate the performance of the proposed Sybil detection framework in VANETs, we utilize both classification-based and communication-based QoS metrics. These include detection accuracy, false positive rate, latency, and PDR, which together provide a comprehensive assessment of the system's reliability and efficiency.

Detection Accuracy: Detection accuracy quantifies the overall correctness of the model in classifying both legitimate and Sybil nodes. It is defined as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

In this formula, TP refers to the number of Sybil nodes correctly identified as Sybil (true positives), TN represents the number of legitimate nodes correctly identified as legitimate (true negatives), FP denotes the number of legitimate nodes incorrectly labeled as Sybil (false positives), and FN indicates the number of Sybil nodes that the model failed to detect (false negatives).

False Positive Rate (FPR): The false positive rate reflects the proportion of legitimate nodes incorrectly flagged as Sybil attackers. This is important in maintaining the trustworthiness and usability of VANET applications:

$$\text{FPR} = \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (2)$$

Minimizing the FPR ensures that legitimate communication is not disrupted and prevents unnecessary warnings or route changes.

Latency Impact: Latency refers to the average time taken for a message to travel from the sender to the receiver. In the context of real-time Sybil detection, it encompasses both the communication and computational delays introduced by the detection mechanism. It is defined as:

$$\text{Latency}_{avg} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (t_{recv}^{(i)} - t_{send}^{(i)}) \quad (3)$$

In this expression, $t_{send}^{(i)}$ denotes the timestamp at which the i -th message was transmitted, $t_{recv}^{(i)}$ is the timestamp at which the same message was successfully received, and N represents the total number of messages delivered.

Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR): PDR quantifies the reliability of the communication network by measuring the proportion of packets that successfully reach their intended destination. It is defined as:

$$\text{PDR} = \frac{P_{delivered}}{P_{sent}} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

In this equation, $P_{delivered}$ denotes the total number of data packets that are correctly received by the intended recipients, while P_{sent} represents the total number of packets originally transmitted by the source nodes.

B. Proposed method

Step 1: Dynamic VANET Graph Modeling: In the proposed model, the VANET is represented as a time-evolving graph that captures the dynamic nature of vehicle movements and communication links:

$$G(t) = (V(t), E(t)) \quad (5)$$

In this model, $V(t) = \{v_1(t), v_2(t), \dots, v_{n(t)}(t)\}$ denotes the set of vehicle nodes present in the network at time t , where $n(t)$ is the number of active vehicles, which can vary due to node mobility. The set $E(t) \subseteq V(t) \times V(t)$ represents the collection of communication links between vehicles at time t . A link $(v_i(t), v_j(t)) \in E(t)$ exists if vehicles v_i and v_j are within communication range.

Each node $v_i(t) \in V(t)$ periodically broadcasts cooperative awareness messages, commonly known as beacon messages, to nearby vehicles. The beacon structure at time t is defined as:

$$m_i(t) = (ID_i, Loc_i(t), Speed_i(t), Dir_i(t)) \quad (6)$$

In this formulation, ID_i represents the globally unique identifier of node v_i , $Loc_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denotes its geographic location at time t , $Speed_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^+$ corresponds to its instantaneous velocity, and $Dir_i(t) \in [0, 2\pi)$ specifies its directional heading expressed in radians. However, these messages can be exploited by adversaries. A Sybil attacker node $v_s(t) \in V(t)$ may fabricate multiple fictitious identities, represented as:

$$\mathcal{I}_s(t) = \{ID_s^1, ID_s^2, \dots, ID_s^k\} \quad (7)$$

Here, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ is the number of Sybil identities generated by the attacker at time t . Each identity impersonates a different vehicle by broadcasting forged beacon messages of the form:

$$m_s^j(t) = (ID_s^j, Loc_s^j(t), Speed_s^j(t), Dir_s^j(t)) \quad (8)$$

Even though the Sybil messages mimic legitimate nodes, they typically originate from the same physical attacker, which results in behavioral patterns that are correlated or inconsistent with normal traffic flow.

Step 2: Data Acquisition and Pre-processing: Vehicular data is collected via V2X-enabled simulations, where each instance captures a vehicle's behavior and is labeled as legitimate (0) or Sybil (1):

$$D = \left\{ \left(\mathbf{x}^{(i)}, y^{(i)} \right) \right\}_{i=1}^N \quad (9)$$

Here, $\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denotes the feature vector of vehicle i , and $y^{(i)} \in \{0, 1\}$ is the class label. Each feature vector includes temporal statistics from beacon messages:

$$\mathbf{x}^{(i)} = \left[\Delta Loc_i, \Delta Speed_i, \Delta Dir_i, f_{beacon}^{(i)}, Trust_i \right] \quad (10)$$

Where $\Delta Loc_i = \|Loc_i(t) - Loc_i(t - \delta t)\|$, $\Delta Speed_i = |Speed_i(t) - Speed_i(t - \delta t)|$, and $\Delta Dir_i = |Dir_i(t) - Dir_i(t - \delta t)|$ represent changes in location, speed, and direction over interval δt ; $f_{beacon}^{(i)}$ is the beacon frequency, and $Trust_i$ is an optional trust score.

Step 3: Feature Engineering for Real-Time Detection: Building on the dynamic VANET graph $G(t)$ defined in Step 1 and the pre-processed data representation from Step 2, each vehicle node is characterized by a set of temporal and relational features that are updated online within a sliding window $[t - \delta t, t]$. These features capture both self-behavioral variations and local neighborhood interactions.

$$\mathbf{x}^{(i)} = \left[\Delta Loc_i, \Delta Speed_i, \Delta Dir_i, f_{beacon}^{(i)}, Trust_i, SimScore_i, \right] \quad (11)$$

Here, ΔLoc_i , $\Delta Speed_i$, and ΔDir_i quantify short-term changes in motion dynamics; $f_{beacon}^{(i)}$ denotes the beacon transmission frequency; $Trust_i \in [0, 1]$ represents a locally computed trust score derived from recent communication consistency; and $SimScore_i \in [0, 1]$ measures behavioral similarity between node v_i and its spatial neighbors in the VANET graph.

Local Similarity Computation: To preserve online and decentralized operation, similarity is computed using *local k-means clustering* at each time step. Nodes are grouped according to standardized motion features:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Distance}(i, j) = & \alpha_1 \|\tilde{Loc}_i - \tilde{Loc}_j\| \\ & + \alpha_2 |\tilde{Speed}_i - \tilde{Speed}_j| + \alpha_3 |\tilde{Dir}_i - \tilde{Dir}_j| \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where each term (denoted by $\tilde{\cdot}$) is *z-score normalized* to zero mean and unit variance within the current time window, ensuring balanced scaling among spatial, velocity, and directional components. For each node v_i , a similarity score is computed as:

$$SimScore_i = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}_i|} \sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \exp\left(-\frac{\text{Distance}(i, j)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (13)$$

where \mathcal{N}_i denotes the set of nodes in the same local cluster, and σ controls the kernel width. Higher $SimScore_i$ values indicate strong motion-pattern correlation among neighboring vehicles.

Step 4: Dataset Labeling and Balancing: For supervised learning, each feature vector must be assigned a binary label indicating whether it belongs to a legitimate or Sybil node. The label $y^{(i)}$ for the i -th sample is defined as:

$$y^{(i)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } v_i \text{ is a Sybil node,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

This binary labeling enables the learning algorithm to distinguish between normal and malicious behaviors.

Step 5: XGBoost Model Formulation: To detect Sybil attacks, the proposed framework employs the XGBoost algorithm, an ensemble of K regularized decision trees trained in an additive manner. For an input feature vector $\mathbf{x}^{(i)}$, the model prediction is obtained as:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{k=1}^K f_k(\mathbf{x}^{(i)}), \quad f_k \in \mathcal{F}, \quad (15)$$

where each tree f_k maps input features to an intermediate score (logit), later transformed into a probability through the sigmoid function. The overall objective combines the logistic loss with a regularization term that penalizes overly complex trees:

$$\mathcal{L}(\Theta) = \sum_{i=1}^N \ell(y^{(i)}, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_{k=1}^K \Omega(f_k), \quad (16)$$

$$\ell(y^{(i)}, \hat{y}_i) = -y^{(i)} \log(\sigma(\hat{y}_i)) - (1 - y^{(i)}) \log(1 - \sigma(\hat{y}_i)), \quad (17)$$

$$\Omega(f_k) = \gamma T_k + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \|w_k\|_2^2, \quad (18)$$

where $\sigma(z) = 1/(1 + e^{-z})$ denotes the sigmoid activation, T_k is the number of leaves in tree f_k , and w_k is the vector of leaf weights. The hyperparameters γ and λ control model sparsity and L2 regularization, respectively.

Step 6: Model Training and Optimization: To optimize the XGBoost model, the objective function $\mathcal{L}(\Theta)$ defined in Eq. (16) is minimized through additive, gradient-based boosting. At each boosting iteration t , a new regression tree f_t is fitted to the negative gradient of the loss, thereby refining the model prediction:

$$\mathcal{L}^{(t)} = \sum_{i=1}^N \ell(y^{(i)}, \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)} + f_t(\mathbf{x}^{(i)})) + \Omega(f_t), \quad (19)$$

where $\hat{y}_i^{(t-1)}$ represents the cumulative prediction for instance i up to iteration $t - 1$, and $f_t(\cdot)$ is the tree learned at the current round. The loss function $\ell(\cdot, \cdot)$ is differentiable (logistic in this work), and the optimization employs a second-order Taylor expansion of $\mathcal{L}^{(t)}$ to efficiently estimate the split gain and leaf weights.

Step 7: Inference and Decision Rule: After training, the XGBoost model produces a real-valued output score \hat{y}_i for each input sample $\mathbf{x}^{(i)}$. This score is converted into a probability estimate via the sigmoid function:

$$P(y = 1 | \mathbf{x}^{(i)}) = \sigma(\hat{y}_i) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\hat{y}_i}}. \quad (20)$$

For binary classification, a decision threshold $\tau \in (0, 1)$ is defined as:

$$\hat{y}_{\text{pred}}^{(i)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } P(y = 1 | \mathbf{x}^{(i)}) \geq \tau, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

The threshold τ is determined using a validation set, selected to maximize the F1-score or to achieve a desired trade-off between TPR and FPR.

IV. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The proposed Sybil detection framework was evaluated using a labeled dataset generated in the OMNeT++ simulator integrated with the Veins framework under IEEE 802.11p communication. The simulation modeled an urban environment of approximately 5 km² containing 35 vehicles operating for 300 s. A subset of the vehicles acted as Sybil attackers that transmitted falsified identity information with varied motion and communication behaviors to emulate realistic adversarial conditions. Each vehicle periodically broadcast beacon messages at 10 Hz, containing position, speed, and direction data.

Beacon logs were collected throughout the simulation, and spatio-temporal features were extracted using a sliding window of $\delta t = 1$ s to capture motion dynamics and neighborhood similarity metrics for each vehicle node.

The resulting dataset consisted of several tens of thousands of labeled records, including both legitimate and Sybil samples. A stratified 70/30 train–test split was applied to preserve class proportions and ensure that data from the same time

segments and vehicles did not overlap across splits. To address class imbalance, sampling strategies were applied within the training subset while keeping the test data unchanged. To mitigate class imbalance, appropriate sampling strategies were applied within the training subset while keeping the test data unchanged.

A. Results

Table I presents the Sybil detection performance in terms of Accuracy and FPR across various simulation scenarios, including different vehicle densities and attacker configurations. As the number of vehicles increases from 10 to 35, the detection accuracy generally remains above 93%, demonstrating the scalability of the proposed XGBoost-based model. Notably, integrating both trust scores and similarity scores significantly improves accuracy and reduces FPR across all densities. For instance, in the 15-car scenario, enabling these features achieves 96.3% accuracy with only 3.8% FPR, while removing similarity scoring leads to a sharp FPR increase to 7.4%. Additionally, mobility patterns also affect performance; low-mobility (highway) scenarios yield higher accuracy (97.2%) and lower FPR (3.1%) compared to high-mobility (urban) environments.

TABLE I
DETECTION ACCURACY AND FPR UNDER DIFFERENT SIMULATION SCENARIOS

Scenario	Accuracy (%)	FPR (%)
Vehicle Density: 10 Cars		
10% Sybil Nodes	94.5	5.6
With Trust + SimScore	95.1	4.9
Vehicle Density: 15 Cars		
10% Sybil Nodes	96.3	3.8
20% Sybil Nodes	94.7	5.2
Without SimScore	91.8	7.4
With Trust + SimScore	96.3	3.8
Vehicle Density: 25 Cars		
20% Sybil Nodes	94.0	5.9
High Mobility (Urban)	95.4	4.6
Low Mobility (Highway)	97.2	3.1
Vehicle Density: 35 Cars		
20% Sybil Nodes	93.5	6.3
With Trust + SimScore	95.9	4.1

Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between the number of nodes and the average delay per communication interface, measured in milliseconds. As the number of nodes increases, the average delay exhibits an upward trend, rising from approximately 26 ms at 5 nodes to just over 40 ms at 35 nodes. This increase is primarily due to higher contention for channel access, an increased frequency of beacon message exchanges, and additional computational overhead introduced by real-time Sybil detection and classification. These results underscore the scalability challenges faced in VANET environments, particularly when implementing security frameworks that require timely processing and communication. Ensuring real-time responsiveness under such conditions remains a critical design consideration.

Figure 3 illustrates the effect of increasing node density on the PDR in a VANET environment. As the number of nodes

Fig. 2. Delay in different scenario

Fig. 3. PDR in different scenario

increases from 5 to 35, the PDR exhibits a gradual decline. At lower densities, such as 5 nodes, the PDR approaches 99.9%, indicating near-optimal message delivery. However, as network density rises, the PDR decreases to approximately 98.3% at 35 nodes. This downward trend can be attributed to increased communication overhead, a higher likelihood of packet collisions, and network congestion—factors that are more pronounced in denser vehicular networks. Despite the integration of Sybil attack detection mechanisms, these underlying scalability challenges slightly impact the overall delivery reliability.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we proposed a real-time and scalable framework for detecting Sybil attacks in Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs) by using spatio-temporal learning and the

XGBoost classification algorithm. Modeling VANETs as dynamic time-evolving graphs allows us to extract key behavioral features such as displacement, speed variation, directional change, beacon frequency, trust scores, and similarity-based clustering. This approach enables accurate differentiation between legitimate vehicles and malicious Sybil identities. The proposed method was evaluated using a comprehensive OMNeT++ simulation environment that mimicked realistic urban traffic scenarios. Results confirmed that the model achieves high detection accuracy (above 96%), low false positive rates (as low as 3.1%), and maintains low inference latency (under 40 ms), ensuring its suitability for real-time applications.

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